

2:6-DIARYL-3-ETHOXYCARBONYL-4-PIPERIDONES AND THEIR DERIVATIVES

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Ten new 2:6-diaryl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-4-piperidones have been synthesised from ethyl acetoacetate, aromatic aldehydes and ammonia in glacial acetic acid, and their properties as well as characteristic group reactions leading to various derivatives have been studied.

Noller *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 3853) prepared a number of substituted 4-piperidones by condensing ethyl acetoacetate with aromatic aldehydes and ammonium acetate in glacial acetic acid in order to study their analgesic properties.

m-Hydroxybenzaldehyde, vanillin, cinnamaldehyde, salicylaldehyde, *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde, *p*-tolualdehyde, veratraldehyde, *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde, furfural and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde have now been employed in the preparation of 2:6-diaryl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-4-piperidones. The maximum yield of 97% has been obtained in the case of furfural and minimum yield (70%) in the case of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde.

The characteristic hydrochlorides of piperidones have been prepared and the carbonyl group condensed with 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine, yielding 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones. Condensation with phenylhydrazine and hydroxylamine has yielded substituted pyrazolones and isoxazolones respectively which may show a complex pattern of pharmacodynamic behaviour.

Finally the reactive methylene group has been successfully condensed with benzaldehyde. Thus, the structure of the substituted 4-piperidones has been corroborated by preparation of characteristic derivatives and analyses.

EXPERIMENTAL

2:6-Diaryl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-4-piperidones.—A mixture of ethyl acetoacetate (0.25 M), aromatic aldehyde (0.5 M) and ammonium acetate (0.5 M) in glacial acetic acid (35 c.c.) was heated under reflux at different temperatures and time intervals (vide Table I). At the end of the reaction the contents were dissolved in ether and a current of dry hydrogen chloride was passed into it for 15 minutes. The hydrochloride so formed was dissolved in a suitable organic solvent and decomposed with ammonia (conc.) at 0° to precipitate the free base. The data regarding the properties and analyses are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	Aldehyde condensed.	Refluxed for. at.	Yield.	Solvent of cryst.	Colour.	M P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen. Found. Calc.	
1.	<i>m</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde	1 hr. 110°	80%	Benzene-pet. ether	Yellow	167°	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ O ₅ N	3.85	3.89
2.	Vanillin	1.5 100°	90	Pet. ether	Yellowish brown	120°	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ O ₇ N	3.35	3.40
3.	Cinamaldehyde	2 100°	86	Do	Brown	112°	C ₂₄ H ₂₅ O ₃ N	3.72	3.75
4.	Salicylaldehyde	1.5 160°	80	Benzene-pet. ether	Yellowish brown	176°	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ O ₅ N	3.88	3.89
5.	<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	1 160°	82	Methanol	Yellow	170°	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₇ N ₂	10.20	10.15
6.	<i>p</i> -Tolualdehyde	4 190°	77	Ethanol-ether	Pale yellow	135°	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ O ₃ N	3.86	3.87
7.	Veratraldehyde	2.5 160°	85	*	Brown	110°	C ₂₄ H ₂₉ O ₇ N	3.18	3.16
8.	<i>p</i> -Dimethylamino-benzaldehyde	2.5 97°	93	Acetone	Yellowish brown	110°	C ₂₄ H ₃₁ O ₃ N ₂	10.38	10.27
9.	Furfural	3 98°	97	Methanol	Violet	105°	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₃ N	4.63	4.65
10.	2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde	2.5 100°	70	Do	Black	111°	C ₂₈ H ₂₅ O ₅ N	3.07	3.28

*Dissolution in phenol and precipitation with alcohol.

2:6-Diaryl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-4-piperidone Hydrochloride.—The piperidone (2 g.) was dissolved in benzene or ether (20 c.c.) and to this HCl (conc., 10 c.c.) was added. The precipitated hydrochloride was filtered and recrystallised from rectified spirit. Relevant data are recorded in Table II.

2:6-Diaryl-3-carbethoxy-4-piperidone-2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone.—The compound was prepared as usual and after filtration and drying was crystallised from ethanol and ether (1:1). The required data are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

No.	Yield.	M.P.	Diaryl-piperidone hydrochlorides.		Phenylhydrazones.			
			Formula.	% Chlorine. Found. Calc.	Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen. Found. Calc.
1	75%	150°	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₅ NC1	8.98 9.06	60%	105°	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ O ₅ N ₅	12.90 13.08
2	80	178°	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ O ₇ NC1	7.82 7.86	65	89°	C ₂₈ H ₂₉ O ₁₀ N ₅	11.82 11.76
3	70	104°	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ O ₃ NC1	8.78 8.80	70	95°	C ₃₀ H ₂₉ O ₅ N ₅	12.66 12.67
4	65	105°	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₃ NC1	9.05 9.07	50	100°	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ O ₅ N ₅	12.90 13.10
5	75	165°	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₇ N ₃ Cl	7.84 7.88	68	99°	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ O ₁₀ N ₇	16.46 16.50
6	80	148°	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ O ₃ NC1	8.98 9.16	70	120°	C ₂₅ H ₂₉ O ₅ N ₅	13.15 13.20
7	85	180°	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₇ NC1	7.44 7.40	60	108°	C ₃₀ H ₂₃ O ₁₀ N ₅	11.30 11.23
8	80	190°	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	7.92 7.96	64	109°	C ₃₀ H ₂₅ O ₅ N ₇	16.68 16.63
9	68	185°	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₃ NC1	10.44 10.46	60	115°	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ O ₅ N ₅	14.39 14.46
10	65	205°	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ O ₅ NC1	7.26 7.23	50	125°	C ₃₄ H ₂₉ O ₅ N ₅	10.95 11.02

*The number corresponds to the respective aldehydes as in Table I.

2: 6 *Diaryl-3:4-piperidophenylhydrazone*.—The appropriate piperidone (0.1 M) and phenylhydrazine (0.1 M) were refluxed in an oil-bath at 125° for 1½ hours. After the reaction, the contents were cooled and treated with alcohol. Most of the fatty matter dissolved leaving behind greyish white solids. These were filtered and crystallised from a suitable solvent. The data regarding properties and analyses are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

Aldehydes.*	Solvent of cryst.	Yield.	Colour.	M P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
						Found.	Calc.
No. 1	Acetone	80%	Violet	160°	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₃	10.41	10.53
2	Chloroform	75	Yellow	128°	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ O ₅ N ₃	9.19	9.15
3	Acetone	80	Dirty white	131°	C ₂₈ H ₂₅ ON ₃	9.98	10.02
4	Do	60	Brown	150°	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₃	10.48	10.53
5	Chloroform	70	Do	146°	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₅	15.31	15.31
6	Chloroform- methanol	75	Green	152°	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ ON ₃	10.53	10.60
7	Methanol	76	Yellow	138°	C ₂₆ H ₂₉ O ₅ N ₃	8.66	8.62
8	Chloroform	75	Orange	142°	C ₂₇ H ₃₁ ON ₅	15.52	15.45
9	Acetone	85	Brown	166°	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃	11.89	12.10
10	Do	65	Black	280°	C ₃₂ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₃	8.39	8.41

*The number corresponds to the respective aldehydes shown in Table I.

2: 6-*Diaryl-3:4-piperido-isoxazolone*.—A mixture of the piperidone (0.2 M), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.2 M), sodium acetate (0.3 M) and absolute alcohol (15 c.c.) was refluxed on a water-bath for 2½ hours. At the end of the reaction, the contents were poured into ice-cold water (100 c.c.) and stirred well. The precipitate was filtered and crystallised from a suitable solvent. Relevant data are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Aldehydes.	Solvent of cryst.	Yield.	Colour.	M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
						Found.	Calc.
No. 1.	Methanol	75%	Yellow	167°	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂	8.60	8.65
2.	Do	70	Green	150°	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₂	7.32	7.25
3.	Acetone	75	Yellow	168°	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₂	7.95	8.11
4.	Methanol	75	Brown	170°	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂	8.58	8.65
5.	Do	70	Yellow	190°	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₆ N ₄	14.58	14.65
6.	Do	65	Do	185°	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₂	8.62	8.65
7.	Do	70	Do	200°	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ O ₆ N ₂	6.82	6.79
8.	Acetone	75	Do	210°	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₄	14.88	14.81
9.	Methanol	78	Violet	250°	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₂	10.33	10.29
10.	Do	75	Do	198°	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ O ₄ N ₂	6.58	6.60

2: 6 *Diaryl-3-carbethoxy-5-benzylidene-4-piperidone*.—The piperidone (0.1 M) was treated with benzaldehyde (0.1 M) and warmed on a water-bath for 10 minutes. On cooling, the product separated and crystallised from chloroform or acetone. The data are recorded in Table V.

TABLE V

Aldehydes.	Yield.	Colour.	M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Calc.
No. 1.	50%	Dirty white	170°	C ₂₇ H ₂₅ O ₃ N	3.15	3.20
2.	55	Do	130°	C ₂₉ H ₂₉ O ₇ N	2.82	2.78
3.	54	Brown	125°	C ₃₁ H ₂₉ O ₃ N	2.89	3.02
4.	60	Do	110°	C ₂₇ H ₂₅ O ₅ N	3.19	3.15
5.	64	Orange	135°	C ₂₇ H ₂₃ O ₇ N ₃	8.39	8.38
6.	68	Colorless	128°	C ₂₉ H ₂₉ O ₃ N	3.08	3.18
7.	60	Do	150°	C ₃₁ H ₃₃ O ₇ N	2.65	2.63
8.	55	Do	155°	C ₃₁ O ₂₅ O ₃ N ₃	8.48	8.45
9.	50	Brown	138°	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ O ₅ N	3.54	3.57
10.	45	Do	146°	C ₃₅ H ₃₅ O ₅ N	2.55	2.58

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